

Report from a Workshop on Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in East Africa, October 2024

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Introduction

In the spring of 2024 representatives from the [Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association](#) (OASPA), the [Directory of Open Access Books](#) (DOAB), [OAPEN](#), and French research institutes in Africa supported by the [National Centre for Scientific Research in France](#) (CNRS) came together to explore engagement with East African publishers about inclusive and sustainable open access book publishing.

As our organisations are engaging actively to better understand and support the African scholarly landscape, a collaborative approach that would gather different perspectives seemed obviously meaningful, and a workshop for East African publishing organisations was scoped.

This online event, held on 24 October 2024, was subdivided into two parts: a webinar offering a range of presentations that would showcase examples of open access activities and initiatives specifically relevant to book publishers, exploring impacts, experiences, revenue models and other topics pertaining to open access book publishing. The second part of the event would consist of a workshop-style format that could facilitate a conversation between the panel of presenters and participants – representing a diverse range of scholarly publishing initiatives from Kenya, Ethiopia, Uganda and Tanzania – on topics raised in the webinar presentations. In this way, a central objective was to share key perspectives from the region and to better understand the contextualised experiences that can help identify the main challenges as well as potential opportunities for accelerating the growth of open access for books in East Africa.

Here we report on the webinar’s presentations, the main themes arising from conversations in the workshop and also consider some next steps. Along with our report from the event below, a [recording of the presentations given on 24 October](#) is also available.

Presentation 1: What would be fair and sustainable open access to books for African studies? Experiences from France and East Africa¹

In the first presentation, Bastien Miraucourt, research engineer and managing editor at CNRS, shared some personal findings and observations of open access books publishing in France and East Africa.

Overseeing the publishing activities of six French research institutes in Sub-Saharan Africa, Bastien gave a brief overview of the institutes' publishing history and, more recently, since the 2010s, the move towards open access activities, with in particular two imprints publishing open access monographs devoted to African studies: *CFEE* (French Center for Ethiopian Studies) for the Horn of Africa and *Africae* for sub-Saharan Africa in general. These publication programmes are fully publicly funded and have open access as a condition: although there is no national open access mandate for books, funding grants for academic publishing, such as the National Open Science Fund, impose open access for books, implying a de facto obligation.

Country of publication of open access monographs on the subject 'Africa', as retrieved from WorldCat searches, 2022. (The colours refer to the respective importance in terms of number of titles).

Posing the question why support such an initiative, an important study by [Cameron Neylon et al. \(2021\)](#) was referenced, showing that a dramatic surge in citations, mentions and downloads were yielded once a book had been 'opened' (i.e. made open access). Importantly in our context is how a vast and geographically diverse readership in the south shows a strong overrepresentation of usage as the African readership is proportionately bigger than North American and European counterparts, despite the small corpus with open access

¹ Data from sources including WorldCat, OAPEN searches and publisher resources. Please watch Bastien's presentation [from the 7th minute onwards in our recording] for a full view of slides, data and references.

African-related subjects.² Open access books with South-related topics have a big chance of attracting a large readership. This data is striking considering that, according to WorldCat, only a meager percentage – around 3% – of books on African topics are open access, which speaks to significant unleashed potential. At the same time, this points to many and significant imbalances in the open access books landscape, one being that open access books by African publishers is severely underrepresented (despite an increase of open access activity in South Africa).

The vast majority of publications on African topics is represented by only a handful of publishers in the US, UK and Germany (Taylor & Francis, Brill, De Gruyter and Springer), with more than half of the books on African topics published in 2022 being by commercial publishers. Further imbalances include the lack of multilingualism (with 95% of books on African studies written in English), with severe underrepresentation of non-Anglophone content deriving from Western, Southern and Central Africa (as the majority of books on African studies focus on English-speaking regions). Another conspicuous imbalance is that authors are mostly based in the Global North; if African, they are employed or affiliated with Global North institutions. Conversely, and to the extent they are based in Africa, they are from Anglophone areas. Research programmes, it was pointed out, are centred and driven from the North, and chances of authoring a book is much bigger if you are a native English speaker, working at a university in the North and conducting research on topics (including within African studies) of interest to the North.

In conclusion, Bastien identified a range of mechanisms that could potentially help support the development of open access for books in the region: online publishing services and open-source software are within reach for implementation, as are existing online journal publishing frameworks and infrastructures, which to some extent can be adopted for books. Dissemination platforms are available and can be further developed locally, as seen with the [African Platform for Open Scholarship](#) at the University of Cape Town. Resources available through initiatives like the [Public Knowledge Project](#) (PKP) – and Open Monographs Press – were also stressed. East African publishers were encouraged to make themselves visible to funders as legitimate academic book publishers and also to explore an assortment of funding models, research grants and crowdfunding opportunities. An important case could also be made for underscoring the principle of inclusion of open access African research to be funded from the North, e.g. through the [European Research Council](#) (ERC), UNESCO, private funding, etc. Finally, the importance of advocacy efforts in relation to funders and policymakers was highlighted, and not least the importance of engaging in networks, collaborative initiatives, consortia and knowledge sharing communities.

2 Data sourced from OpenEdition, <https://logs.openedition.org/> (July 2022); <https://analytics.openedition.org/>

Presentation 2: About some successful open access books funding models

In the second presentation, Judith Fathallah, Senior Research Associate at Lancaster University, presented the work of the [Open Book Collective](#), a UK-based charity with international membership consisting of open access book publishers and service providers. It supports community-led initiatives and aims to enable alternative revenue models to the unsustainable, unscalable, yet still dominant book processing charges (BPCs) that publishers ask for to make a book open. These charges are unaffordable and inaccessible to many researchers, for example early career researchers or researchers working within disciplines or regions where funding is historically sparse.

**Collective, Connected,
Sustainable**

Through the collective's membership scheme, support is solicited from libraries, raising revenue streams for publishers and enabling them to move away from the BPC-reliant model and also fostering bibliodiversity. Similarly, by leveraging support for service providers, crucial infrastructures for open access book publishing can become more sustainable, reliable and also allow for better fiscal planning. By working collaboratively in a collective, small publishers without the necessary resources and capacity to offer a library an attractive membership scheme on their own are supported.

Judith also highlighted the workflows that are set in place to facilitate metadata management, outreach activities undertaken on their behalf and the provision of easy integration with third party payment arrangements. In a complex publishing landscape with a vast array of offers, Judith explained how the Open Book Collective makes it easier for libraries to support open access membership schemes. It does so by serving as an aggregator and discovery portal through which libraries can find consolidated information about initiatives that are relevant to them, while being assured that, for instance, publishers meet high standards for peer review, transparency as to governance and business models.

Judith also briefly introduced the [Open Book Collective's Development Fund](#). The fund supports open access publishers as well as infrastructure providers through a grant-giving scheme to which funds are allocated through a small percentage of membership fees to the Open Book Collective. The scheme is designed to help bolster open access initiatives by supporting the publishing of high-quality academic books, infrastructure, networks, advo-

cacy and capacity building. Open to applications from around the world, the fund places weight on initiatives that seek to foster bibliodiversity, resource sharing, network building and horizontal working.

Presentation 3: Integrating digital outputs and open access in the business development of an academic book publisher in Africa

In the third presentation we heard from Andrew Joseph, the Digital Publisher at [Wits University Press](#), a Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) publisher based in Johannesburg, South Africa, who provided a use case for open access publishing at a university press in the South African context.

Andrew first offered a broad overview of the many attempts amongst South African university and scholarly presses, but also commercial presses, to engage with open access activities, with some being more successful than others. He highlighted the importance of infrastructure and digital outputs for enabling open access.

Increasingly, there have been attempts at alignment and coordination of policies and activities in South Africa, especially post-Covid, but there are challenges in terms of state and institutional mandates in the country. There are strong mandates to publish open access, but the necessary structural support, funding and vital infrastructures are not always forthcoming, so it is very much up to individual publisher initiatives and efforts to drive the open agenda. Andrew pointed to a range of useful resources that are available, such as [PKP \(Open Monograph Press\)](#), an open source, end-to-end solution to manage book publishing, and [OAPEN](#), a discoverability platform, which are very helpful infrastructures that facilitate open access book publishing. Encouraging trends were noted, for instance more backlist flipping, but also more born open titles with the emergence of diamond presses, such as UJ Press and African Minds, which is important both from a production of digital output perspective but also principally good.

Wits University Press is trying to balance mission and a cost-recovery model, but is also committed to publishing at least 10 per cent of its frontlist open access. The press relies on BPCs, which, whilst not sustainable, are an unfortunate necessity if the press must secure institutional support. Andrew emphasised that the press treats open access and non-open access titles on an equal footing in terms of quality or actual product itself, applying the same range of services to all digital formats – i.e. XML workflow, DOIs, persistent identifiers, ONIX generation, marketing and dissemination to support discoverability.

Andrew concluded his presentation by noting some persistent challenges in the region. One concerned the content and processes around high-level open access policymaking and the imperative need to include and consult smaller voices as they are essential to both academic and cultural capital. Including only big voices will be to the neglect of local knowledge production, languages

and HSS, which is currently being overshadowed by the strong focus on journals and STM. The onus for this is on policymakers and publishers.

He pointed to some further positive developments happening in the South African landscape, for example decolonisation initiatives, which is fundamentally a political project aiming to reclaim control and ownership of local content and ensure that attribution not only happens on the level of the author, but also at national levels. Again, the coordinated and collaborative approaches, both regionally and beyond, were highlighted, as well as the importance of publishers and other stakeholder groups taking an active part in emerging conversations and networks. Formation of local and regional consortia was proposed as a possibility to explore in more detail and something to take forward in a South-led initiative.

Presentation 4: First results of an African institutional publisher's global transition to open access

In the webinar's final presentation, Jill Claassen, Section Manager of Scholarly Communication and Research at the [University of Cape Town \(UCT\) Libraries](#), shared a library perspective on open access publishing. Offering an overview of the press' history and context, she explained that since 2021 the press has been operationally located within the UCT library. A fully open access publisher, the press is underpinned by a strong social justice mission that aims to remove access barriers and ensure that research should be as widely disseminated as possible.

Jill explained the press' governance structure within the university, touching on the importance of the academic component, press advocacy and the soliciting of funding from the university, which ensures that the press can function efficiently and sustainably. In terms

of business models, she explained that publishing costs for UCT researchers producing academic work, which meet the South African's Department of Higher

Education research output policy criteria, are carried by the press. However, monographs from non-UCT authors are subject to BPCs.

The commitment of UCT to open access publishing is further reflected by the development of the [African Platform for Open Scholarship](#), a platform making it possible for African researchers to reclaim ownership of local knowledge production and enable sharing of scholarly content and so sustainably grow the African research ecosystem. Such a development aligns with UCT's acknowledgement of linking to diverse global community and the need to support the bidirectional flow of research in order to bridge North-South divides. To this end, one of UCT's priorities is to promote its catalogue, including flipped backlist titles, through their integration in major international indexes and thus visibilise and promote African scholarship.

Also, an expression of international collaboration is seen through it recently becoming a

partner in the [DOAB Trusted Platform Network](#), a discoverability platform that works with partners to disseminate peer reviewed open scholarship and foster bibliodiversity. Further, the UCT Press has recently sought membership of the Open Book Collective, thus supporting alternative revenue and publishing models aligning with their own values focusing on community, sustainability and more equitable pathways within open scholarly communication.

Conversations, connections, continuity

Following the webinar presentations, a workshop was convened with a Q&A session, and a more general conversation among all the participants was encouraged, moderated by Joseph Musakali, professor at the School of Information Sciences, Moi University, Kenya.

It is only natural that many different perspectives and perceptions can be expected in such a context, given that vantage points may vary significantly depending on the type of publishing entity – e.g. library-based publisher, a university press or an independent commercial publisher. The questions fielded during this session very much reflected such variation, which was also defined by geographical location and how engaged and involved, or advanced, the publishing entity is in terms of ongoing conversations about open access. For instance, a small independent publisher only just starting to explore the open access landscape may not be as vocal during such a session as some of the more seasoned initiatives operating within institutional contexts and already familiar with well-known challenges and barriers impeding paths to open access. The latter would directly address questions like how best to overcome the challenges of indexing in mainstream, subscription-based citation databases like Scopus and Web of Science, or how to move beyond or evolve transformative agreements.

Both in the presentation and in the discussion part, the disconnect between journals and books was emphasised in the sense of the former being more developed, which is also the case beyond the African context. Although the session was aimed at addressing longform publishing in particular, questions like these allowed for reflections on how to rethink or propose a different trajectory for books, one that for instance would rely less on inequitable and unscalable business models that have been driving journals, for instance a default application of expensive processing charges and proprietary indexing platforms.

A thread running through the presentations and the discussion was how to effect the necessary changes that will enable viable routes for open access publishing. For instance, a question was asked about what kind of mindset changes are most important in terms of promoting open access models in the African context and ensuring equitable access to reading and publishing. It was stressed that advocacy on all levels is crucial to drive behaviour – of publishers, researchers, librarians, vice chancellors, institutional and national policymakers – by focusing on and stressing the benefits of increasing access to local knowledge production and its potential to mitigate societal challenges and further the common good – in addition to pointing to additional benefits, such as wider distribution and dissemination

of research, more citations and impact. This could also serve as a direct response to one of the questions asked, addressing the motivation for private African publishers in promoting open access publishing.

Mindset changes, it was heard, are sometimes blocked through persistent myths around open access, such as a lack of quality assurance, loss of intellectual property or access to printed copies upon publication. This would tie in to lingering issues relating to prestige and legacy publishing, such as aspiring to publish with particular publishers and the value placed on the idea of royalties as a necessary incentive. Also, authors were encouraged to be more vigilant about their intellectual rights and not yield to pressure to sign away their rights because they may be working within niche disciplines.

Another key takeaway was the strong emphasis on collaboration, both on a local and international level. It is not merely a question of adopting international standards as this simply risks perpetuating the systemic inequities within the scholarly landscape, but rather to engage and help shape the wider open agendas. The University of Cape Town is a good example of a publisher committed to nurturing and promoting African scholarship in an attempt to redress imbalances emanating from the Global North. A common theme supported by all presenters and participants was appreciating that they are all a part of a global scholarly ecosystem and that there is a need for wider coordination, resource sharing and engagement in consort with local and international organisations, through participation in workshops and exploratory open access initiatives, publishers associations, conferences, board meetings etc. Fostering strong relationships and communities in support of open access book publishing is imperative for growing an ecosystem that is viable, sustainable and equitable in the future.

In response to a question of how best to promote open access publishing and develop the necessary support mechanisms, we heard that an institutional environment, such as a library for instance, was ideally positioned to offer such support. Implementing a publishing entity can more readily be adapted within libraries as these, to varying degrees, already have installed capacity as a library publisher with dissemination infrastructures and other services to facilitate such ends, and not only supporting open access, but also to some extent directly funding it. Of course, there is also the in-built expectation (and challenge) that some university presses face that their publishing activities should generate revenues and incomes for the institution. This causes an embedding of subscriptions or less inclusive open access models.

Similar views were expressed by Professor Muliaro Wafula (ICT Centre of Excellence and Open Data, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya), who shared some reflections through an East African perspective and highlighted the importance of extending open access to encompass data and open science. He also championed the need for local research and addressing local challenges. One way of doing this is through a federation of publishers working together, making themselves more visible and collectively facing challenges such as predatory publishing that risk undermining academic publishing.

In an institutional context, it was clear that coordination is of paramount importance, but also awareness raising. The main topics addressed in the discussion circled around funding, institutional structure and the provision of infrastructure and capacity building to facilitate the implementation of functional and sustainable open access resources and programmes. These key ingredients cannot stand alone – a swathe of important aspects such as coordination, research and knowledge sharing, advocacy and the rethinking of incentives and reward systems are equally relevant. It is critical that we consider the wider ecosystem in working to leverage support for open access, but also that nuanced perspectives are applied, respecting disparities and local cultural practices in fostering bibliodiversity. To this end, the promotion of multilingualism and a diversity of voices – not least that of local research – is considered to be essential.

The availability and priority of funding continues to be a key mechanism for driving the open agenda. Although funding is scarce in East Africa (as it is in many other areas) – on national and also institutional levels – the presentations pointed to a variety of alternative and community-driven business models and infrastructures that could serve as inspiration to circumvent traditional paths to open access book publishing and uncoupling expensive and unsustainable per unit charges. From library publishers in an institutional context to small private publishers engaging in open access models that remove per-publication charges, it is important to bear in mind that the removal of a paywall barrier for open access is not synonymous with the absence of publishing costs. Hence financial sustainability is a necessary focal point. The necessary change and transition to open access can happen more expediently in a climate where, for instance, the unnecessary duplication of labour is avoided and in which skills, resources and innovation are freely shared.

The rich presentations and informative discussions successfully delivered on the objectives of the online session: to gain a better understanding of the academic publishing landscape in East Africa – not least the challenges and barriers preventing open access for long-form publications to thrive – and also to probe opportunities for collaboration in the future. Also, through a series of use cases, publishers, libraries and other initiatives gave helpful examples of alternative, values-driven and sustainable routes to open access book publishing. With this comes the acknowledged caveat that there is still much to learn and much work to be done. Many ongoing conversations about open access publishing are taking place in East Africa, in other parts of Africa and further afield. Some work is already being undertaken to identify and map infrastructures and stakeholders in the African context that can help accelerate open access book publishing and foster resource sharing and strengthen advocacy agendas. Further, the establishment of working groups and connecting up local efforts and initiatives could be important when moving forward. Collaborative and community-driven initiatives that engage with many different and relevant voices throughout the entire research ecosystem will promote inclusiveness and diversity. In this way, imbalances, biases and a system fraught with inequities can start being redressed, and more equitable opportunities for knowledge production and exchange enabled.

A word of thanks to each of our presenters, to the moderator for the presentations section of the event, Mary Felix (DOAB and OAPEN), to our workshop-section conversation facilitator, Joseph Juma Musakali (Moi University), and for added reflections from East Africa from Prof. Wafula (JKUAT). We are also grateful to Pierre Mounier for his assistance with preparing the event. Thanks also to our esteemed audience of East African publishers for attending and participating, to Bastien Miracourt for his knowledge and unceasing efforts to connect with publishers in Africa and finally to the EventsHub and OASPA for technology and logistics that enabled this workshop.

The task ahead is to build on the momentum of this and a previous workshop held in Cape Town in February 2024. The organisers and many of the presenters from the East Africa workshop recently attended the [2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#) held in Cape Town in December 2024, where workshop results were presented, and where important issues from the workshops were further [addressed](#).

We, co-organisers of the [Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in East Africa](#) event of October 2024 are keen to continue to support and learn from South-led and locally nurtured initiatives that will help open up scholarly works - in East Africa and beyond.